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A relationship between ERBB gene expression and the TBC1D gene family.

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We studied the relationship between ERBB gene expression and the TBC1D gene family using a cellular system that models acquired resistance to the HER2 chemical inhibitor lapatinib. We describe here strong induction of TBC1D2 and TBC1D32, as well as TBC1D8B and TBC1D16 as a component of the resistance gene signature in human cancer cells. TBC1D4 and TBC1D9 were instead silenced. A TBC gene family signature characterizes the ERBB resistance program *in vitro*.